

FORMATION OF CREATIVITY IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Introduction (preface). The article highlights the main issues related to the formation of creativity among primary school students. Teaching art subjects, in particular art and music lessons in the context of teaching spirituality, is one of the fundamental knowledge acquired in secondary schools. The disciplines of art determine the direction in the development of the environment, based on such concepts of universal human values as philanthropy and morality, which are more capacious and clearly explained by objects of art. At the same time, educating elementary school students in the beginnings of fine arts and the art of music play a major role in mastering the concept of spirituality and morality. Also in the formation of creativity, the need to be vigilant in correctly mastering a given subject is a key approach when teaching various subjects

Research methods. In the process of researching the formation of creativity in the primary grades of secondary schools, problems associated with the introduction of new methods of teaching art disciplines in schools, it should be noted that the fundamental criterion in teaching and forming the consciousness of the beginning of art is the huge role of the teacher. The teacher, based on the knowledge acquired, must have a beneficial effect on the formation of modern art on the consciousness of students using exclusively humane methods.

Research results. The results of a study of the teaching of art disciplines in secondary schools showed that the formation of creativity in primary school students into highly moral individuals is achieved through competent teaching of art subjects. The extraordinary attitude of some teachers about the insignificant role of music and art teachers in the formation of personality forces them to take more drastic measures to raise the level of art subjects in school.

Conclusions. From all that has been said above, quite serious conclusions should be drawn that the teaching of music lessons and fine arts lessons needs to be raised to a higher level. Since art subjects at this stage of teaching in secondary schools are the only disciplines in which the task of developing creative and creative thinking is laid down, the prestige of these subjects (drawing and music) in secondary schools should be raised.

Key words and phrases. Prestige, high level, serious conclusions, highly moral individuals, personality formation.

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